

STATE SUPPORT MEASURES FOR FRUIT AND VEGETABLE AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS

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Abstract. In the article, the cluster method of production in agriculture has been established, the size of the agricultural areas divided into clusters by crop types is 67% in cotton and textile, 8% in animal husbandry, and 7.5% in fruit and vegetable growing. It is analyzed that serious attention should be paid to the organization of interest.

Key words. Advanced technologies, efficiency, strategy, agriculture, viticulture network, organizational and economic mechanisms.

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, consistent measures have been taken to reform agriculture and introduce market mechanisms to the sector.

As a result of the processing of raw materials grown in the cluster method, it is possible to deliver them to the consumer in the form of a finished product.

Today, more than 80 types of agricultural products grown in our republic are exported to 66 countries of the world. In 2010, cotton fiber accounted for 11.3% of exports, but by 2018, this figure decreased to 1.6%.

At the same time, the lack of systematic implementation of effective market mechanisms, especially in the development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture, and the insufficient scientific approach lead to underutilization of the available opportunities of the sector.

According to calculations, it is possible to earn 7 times more from grapes, 6 times from cherries, and 5 times more from walnuts than raw cotton grown on 1 hectare.

Targeted programs for the organization of fruit and vegetable clusters, allocating land areas, attaching farms to them, establishing intensive orchards and vineyards, providing working capital, expanding or building the necessary infrastructure facilities in each potential project section. The one-by-one review and assessment laid the groundwork for effective organization of work in this regard.

In order to correctly assess the possibilities of the regions of the republic, the proposals for the establishment of 86 clusters were thoroughly studied by the experts of the Ministry of Agriculture.

In particular, the following measures are defined for the organization and development of fruit and vegetable clusters. In particular, according to stage 1 (86 clusters):

Applicants forming clusters have their own areas of 18,322 hectares, and 60,519 hectares have been allocated to 7,851 farms.

The area attached to the clusters is 30% of the area of fruit and vegetable cultivation in the respective regions.

In 2020, based on the contracts concluded by the clusters to export 359 thousand 812 tons (342.4 million dollars) of fruits and vegetables and the existing processing capacities, the crops were planted.

In 2022, the export indicators of the selected clusters will be increased by 5 times compared to last year, and the processing indicators will be increased by 2 times.

As a result of these ongoing measures, by 2025, productivity in intensive gardens will be 200 s/ha, in vineyards 150 s/ha, in vegetable growing 29 s/ha, in policing 28 s/ha, in potato growing 23 s/ha and in leguminous crops 7 s/ha is achieved, which in turn makes it possible to reduce the cost of manufactured products and increase competitiveness in export-oriented foreign markets.

It is necessary to create a mechanism of state support for the established clusters, including:

1. Some farms attached to clusters have debts to the budget, and when the cluster makes an advance payment, the budget debts are recovered. Extending the period of payment of debts to such farmers to the budget and state special purpose funds, as well as the collection of fines and fines until this year's harvest;

2. This year, very big plans have been made to create an intensive garden and vineyards. It is known that the investments made in this field in agriculture are intended for a long period of time, and the profit will start to bear fruit after 3 years. Today, the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurs provides practical assistance in providing a guarantee of up to 50% of the collateral for loans allocated for the creation of intensive gardens and vineyards. However, when the guarantee is presented, no concession is given on the loan interest payment. Taking into account the social importance of creating intensive orchards and vineyards for our country and the importance of the export potential, it is necessary to give an opportunity to use both benefits at the same time by our initiators who have formed clusters and farms attached to them.

3. Today, when commercial loans are granted to our farms creating intensive gardens and vineyards, up to 8% of the excess over the refinancing rate of the Central Bank will be compensated for the full term (for 7 years). Entrepreneurs who create an intensive garden or vineyard will have financial difficulties until the created garden or vineyard begins to harvest.

Development of activity of fruit and vegetable clusters and cooperatives

FRUIT AND VEGETABLE CLUSTER

Actions taken	growth rate		
Number of clusters	146	575	
Attached Farmer	9868	15320	+5452
Combined land area (per thousand)	117.5	466	
Land area of farms (per thousand)	87	351	+264
Land area divided into clusters (per thousand)	30.5	115	+84,5
Number of jobs, (a thousand people)	22	132	+110
Engaged investment, (mlrd.dollar)	128	320	+192
Processing steps coverage, (%)	15	50	+35
Export volume	575		

- agricultural associations, ensuring mutual cooperation of farmers and peasant farms with clusters;
- supporting various forms of associations: clusters, cooperatives and production associations;
- determination of measures for the development and promotion of clusters in all sectors.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In Uzbekistan, fruit orchards, especially orchards using the intensive method, are not organized enough, orchards and vineyards have fallen into disrepair, their economic efficiency is extremely low, and thousands of hectares of old orchards in a number of districts have not produced crops for years. The cooperative system that forms the chain of "production - purchase - storage and processing - export" has not yet been introduced. SHAVKAT MIRZIYOEV

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